

Thematic Digital Competence Centers

Application form

1. General information

1a. Project title

Towards a Modular Infrastructure for Comprehensive RDM (MICR)

1b. Relevant Thematic DCC Domain

- Life Sciences and Health (LSH)
- Natural and Engineering Sciences (NES)
- Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)

1c. Project duration

18 months.

1d. Responsible institution(s) and department

Amsterdam University Medical Centre (ICT)

Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (Library, ICT)

CLARIAH (SSHOC-NL)

DANS (Data Station SSH)

DCC-PO (Central Coordination)

Erasmus University Rotterdam (School of Social and Behavioural Sciences)

KNAW (RDM & Digital Infrastructure, Humanities Cluster)

LCRDM (Central Coordination)

Leiden University (Information Management, ICT)

Maastricht University (Chief Open Science)

ODISSEI (SSHOC-NL)

Radboud University (Library, Faculty of Social Sciences – Donders Institute)

SURF (Research Data Management, Research Innovation)

Tilburg University (Library, ICT)

TU Delft (Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment)

TU Eindhoven (LIS, Product Area Research)

University of Amsterdam (Fac. of Social and Behavioural Sciences, Fac. of Humanities, ICT, Library)

University of Groningen (Library)

University of Humanistic Studies (Graduate School, Research & Valorisation)

University of Twente (ICT)

Utrecht University (Social and Behavioural Sciences, ICT)

VU Amsterdam (Library, ICT)

Wageningen University & Research (Library)

1e. Lead applicant and co-applicants

Title, first name, initials, surname	Affiliation	Department	Role(s)
Frans Oort	UvA	FMG	Lead applicant
Maarten Hoogerwerf	SURF	Research Innovation	Co-applicant
Marcel Ras	VU	UB	Co-applicant

*Note: Applicants will be members of the steering group.

1f. Keywords

Infrastructure, RDM, FAIR, modular systems, fit-gap analysis.

1g. Disciplines

	Discipline*:
Main discipline:	40.40.00 Psychonomic and Cognitive Psychology
Other disciplines (if applicable):	45.90.00 Sociology
	42.00.00 Pedagogics
	30.90.00 Linguistics, other

*Note: The project covers as many disciplines in the SSH domain as possible. Given the multidisciplinary nature of the SSH domain, the results may also be applicable to disciplines in the Life & Health Sciences.

1h. Abstract (max. 500 words)

Dutch research institutes have policies or guidelines for RDM in the SSH domain¹. However, in many cases SSH institutes and parties, such as CLARIAH and ODISSEI (cooperating in SSHOC-NL), are unable to offer the complete infrastructure required for implementing their RDM policies, including Open Science and FAIR data principles. Moreover, RDM infrastructure should not only comply with policies but also be use-friendly and appropriate, thereby reducing workload for both researchers and support staff, while also providing management information.

RDM infrastructure should support and guide the research journey from start to finish. In the beginning, this includes creating a data management plan. Thereafter, it involves collecting, processing, and analysing (re-usable) data. Towards the end, FAIR archiving and publication of data are important and controlling access to data for re-use. However, current RDM infrastructure is lacking or suboptimal in supporting the entire research journey. For instance, to collaborate on data analyses, to archive sensitive and big data for the long-term, to make data publications FAIR, or to facilitate re-use of data by providing controlled access. There are several initiatives trying to tackle certain challenges, such as RDX² and DAB³, Yoda⁴ and FAIR Data Hub⁵, or SANE⁶ and ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer⁷. However, these solutions are developed separately, often for specific features, which complicates efforts to achieve a comprehensive and integrated IT landscape that fully supports RDM.

We aim to identify which infrastructure components are of common interest for RDM improvement, to sharpen the focus for a joint effort developing these components. Not all institutes will be interested in the same identified components. Therefore, not only interoperability but also modularity is of importance, enabling institutes to select the components they want to use. At the same time, we need to ensure alignment with international infrastructures provided by EOSC.

We propose to: (1) explore the extent to which institutes share the same RDM policies; (2) study a selection of existing SSH research projects (i.e., complementary use cases) to understand the context and difficulties when RDM solutions insufficient or disconnected; (3) create an inventory of available RDM infrastructures; (4) perform (fit-gap) analyses with the policies, use cases and inventory as

¹ For an example of general RDM policy principles, see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10954657>

² For a short explanation of the RDX, see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8269273>

³ For a short explanation of the DAB, see: <https://dab.surf.nl/about/>

⁴ For more information on Yoda, see: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/yoda>

⁵ For a short description of the FDH, see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11201003>

⁶ For a short explanation of SANE, see: <https://www.surf.nl/sane-secure-environment-for-analysing-sensitive-data>

⁷ For more information on OSSC, see: <https://odissei-data.nl/nl/facility/veilig-computergebruik>

guidelines to identify common needs for further RDM developments; (5) provide recommendations for harmonisation and co-development of RDM solutions in the SSH domain.

We are aware of the challenges in fully covering the diverse SSH domain. Through engagement with the SSH community and reflections on representativeness, the recommendations will be relevant to the vast majority of the SSH domain and probably beyond. Finally, we will also propose how underrepresented disciplines can be included in the future.

1i. Public project title and public summary

NL

Op Weg naar een Modulaire Infrastructuur voor Allesomvattende RDM

Veel onderzoeksinstituten hebben RDM-beleid voor het SSH-domein, maar missen toegankelijke infrastructuur om dat beleid volledig te implementeren. Momenteel ontwikkelen zij, vaak met beperkte middelen en onafhankelijk van elkaar, diverse lokale RDM-infrastructuren. Een gezamenlijke landelijke inspanning is noodzakelijk om een beleidsconforme, modulaire en interoperabele infrastructuur te creëren, waaruit instituten de best passende componenten kunnen kiezen. Om dit te bereiken, moeten de tekortkomingen in de huidige RDM-infrastructuur worden vastgesteld. Wij stellen voor om het bestaande beleid en de ondersteunende infrastructuren te identificeren, zodat hiaten zichtbaar worden en aanbevelingen kunnen volgen voor toekomstige gezamenlijke RDM-innovaties binnen het SSH-domein.

ENG

Towards a Modular Infrastructure for Comprehensive RDM

Many research institutes have RDM policies for the SSH domain, but lack the infrastructure to fully implement them. Currently, they are independently developing different local RDM infrastructures, often with limited resources. A concerted nationwide effort would be helpful to create a policy-compliant, modular and interoperable infrastructure from which institutes can choose the appropriate components. To achieve this, the shortcomings of the current RDM infrastructure need to be identified. We propose to examine existing policies and supporting infrastructures to identify the gaps, so that recommendations can follow for future collaborative RDM innovations within the SSH domain.

2. Project information

2.1 Involvement of TDCC domain in drafting application (max. 400 words)

Initiated by stakeholders from the UvA, interest in the project was gauged nationally by reaching out via mailing lists, forums, and contacts of the DCC Implementation Network, the TDCC-SSH, LCRDM, DSIG, and the UNL organisation of Chiefs Open Science. In parallel, we approached individuals from academic institutions and service providers to brainstorm and establish collaborations. This led to a series of meetings with representatives of these organisations (academic institutions, SURF, DANS, LCRDM) to discuss the goals and scope of the project, as well as how to relate to other ongoing initiatives and domains to ensure mutual viability and avoid duplication.

In preparation for the organised public sessions, our consortium invited anyone within their networks who was interested to join. After receiving feedback from the review committee, we updated the national network through the previously mentioned national community tools (mailing lists, forums) and hosted two public sessions for further discussion. Newly interested parties, such as DCC-PO and SSHOC-NL representatives, joined the discussion on how to implement the committee's feedback and how to further connect with other stakeholders in the SSH domain. Based on community input, we continued our outreach to invite additional academic institutions and service providers to participate (academic institutions, ODISSEI, CLARIAH, KNAW).

A small group of representatives took the lead in the writing process, while a larger group of people reviewed the proposal. This transparent and community-driven approach has helped to minimise bias. The result is a project that reflects the opinions and interests of the consortium and aims to address pressing issues in the 'FAIRification' of data and software by providing recommendations for developing comprehensive and modular RDM infrastructure, which is most advantageous for SSH.

This TDCC-SSH Challenge project was developed alongside other initiatives in Bottleneck, Challenge and OSNL calls. Our goal is to facilitate knowledge exchange and foster constructive interaction where feasible between SSH initiatives and other existing consortia. The project is connected to two SSH-Bottleneck projects (SLPPRS-NL and 'Untangling FAIR implementation in the Dutch SSH')⁸, the Yoda consortium, SSHOC-NL, and is linked with the UNL organisation of Chiefs Open Science (UNL COS). The 'research' centred outcomes of this project provide a better understanding of what is needed for SSH and can be used to direct the development of a more effective RDM infrastructure. Therefore, they can be used as starting point for upcoming OSNL projects.

2.2 Roadmap ambition/activity cluster/challenge

NES	SSH	LSH
<input type="checkbox"/> FAIR data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAIRification of data and software	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthen good data stewardship and harmonise data access practises
<input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable software and e-science	<input type="checkbox"/> Raising awareness	<input type="checkbox"/> Enhance the interoperability of digital solutions and resources
<input type="checkbox"/> Connections to the international activities	<input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge enhancement	<input type="checkbox"/> Strengthen the capacity and expertise base in digital research
<input type="checkbox"/> Long-term data archiving	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Addressing pressing issues	
<input type="checkbox"/> Locate computing capacity close to the storage	<input type="checkbox"/> Building a network	
<input type="checkbox"/> Human capital		
<input type="checkbox"/> Cross-field collaborations		

2.3 Relevance (max. 400 words)

Impact and Urgency of the Project

Researchers are not provided with the necessary resources to fully comply with the policies and guidelines of their institutes, and the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. Additionally, data management must meet regulatory requirements, and address sovereignty concerns to protect the interests of SSH institutes. In the context of Open Science, all data should be archived with full provenance in a closed archive (FAIR for the institute) and data suitable for publication should be published on an open platform (FAIR for the outside world)⁹.

To work according to these conditions, researchers need a user-friendly and well-supported RDM infrastructure, which facilitates their RDM activities and makes it effortless to comply. This infrastructure includes components such as data management, archiving support, and platforms for publishing research data. Moreover, to safeguard data sovereignty, data access must be carefully regulated. Ultimately, developing a nationally recognised, modular, and comprehensive RDM infrastructure will enhance the FAIRification of research data, promote Open Science, improve support, strengthen security, ensure legal compliance, and most importantly aid researchers and support staff in their work. However, first it is necessary to determine which available RDM

⁸ For a short description of both Bottleneck projects, see: <https://tdcc.nl/tdcc-ssh-bottleneck-projects/>

⁹ For an example of general RDM policy principles, see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10954657>

infrastructures are ineffective for implementing policies and need innovation. This will be the main focus of this project. The outcomes can be used to optimise (co)development efforts leading to a widely (re-)useable RDM infrastructure for the SSH domain.

Alignment with the Ambitions of the TDCC Roadmaps

This project addresses three key challenges outlined in the TDCC roadmaps by providing recommendations to tackle these in future developments:

1. Support: Improving the RDM infrastructure involves creating streamlined, integrated, and largely automated support workflows that improve communication, develop documentation and training, and encourage adoption of RDM products and services.
2. Sensitive data: Improving the RDM infrastructure enables researchers and institutes to manage their data effectively, ensuring easy access to relevant sources and supporting the management of sensitive data. It also increases FAIR access through secure data exchange, enforced terms of use, and diverse access policies.
3. FAIR data and software: Currently, a significant amount of valuable data is still not being made available. An appropriate RDM infrastructure provides researchers with the support and services needed to archive and publish their (meta)data distinguishing between FAIR for the world (open) and FAIR for the institute (closed).

2.4 Project outline including work packages (max. 1600 words)

This project will focus on exploring RDM policies and supporting infrastructures in all research phases to provide recommendations to shape future RDM developments more effectively for the SSH domain. However, given the multidisciplinary nature of SSH, the results may also apply to other domains such as the 'Life & Health' sciences. We will be aware of possible generalisations to other domains.

The project is divided into three work packages (WPs).

In short, the first package (WP1) has responsibility to manage and support the project and engage the SSH community. The second package (WP2) is responsible for the modelling and (fit-gap) analyses of the data from the inventory. Additionally, it is responsible for the recommendations on future developments of RDM infrastructure components and integrations. The third package (WP3) is responsible for the inventory of policy, infrastructure and known bottlenecks of the participating institutes, both via contextualised use cases (from both humanities and social sciences) and via a more quantitative approach.

Engagement is an essential component of this project. The engagement activities include:

- Involvement of the wider SSH and RDM community to support and streamline (iterative) reviews and discussions of the deliverables. This will be facilitated through WP1.
- Involvement of institutes and other stakeholders such as ODISSEI, CLARIAH, SURF, DANS with the help of the (DCC) contact persons to organise and perform the inventories within their institutes/ organisations. This will be done through WP1 and WP3.
- Collaboration and information exchange with the TDCC-SSH Bottleneck projects 'SLIPPRS-NL' and 'Untangling FAIR implementation in the Dutch SSH' will take place, because these projects can benefit from each other's efforts. These projects share activities collecting and analysing FAIR-enabling policies and practices from various stakeholders across the country. To avoid redundant efforts, we will coordinate our activities and leverage each other's expertise. This will be done through WP1 and WP3.

Oversight and guidance will be provided by a steering committee composed of the main applicants and representatives of national stakeholders. Who these representatives are, has to be decided and this is one of the first deliverables of WP1.

The work effort of the project manager/coordinator, business analysts/architects, and data stewards will be charged to the project. The work of the contact persons will be considered as an in-kind contribution (see project budget).

The figure below illustrates the three WPs.

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the work packages.

Below are the descriptions of the work packages in more detail.

Work Package 1 (WP1): Project Management and Engagement (coordination led by UvA)

WP1 contains the activities related to project coordination, planning, and documentation. It also involves engaging and maintaining contact with institutes, organisations, and communities in the SSH domain. In addition, WP1 supports the project team (i.e. the other roles in the project) in carrying out their work. Finally, WP1 monitors progress and ensures that all work packages remain aligned.

Activities:

- Forming steering committee (applicants and representatives of national organisations) and keeping them informed.
- Formulating project and communication plan.
- Engaging and informing stakeholders in the SSH domain.
- Facilitating the project for completing the work packages.
- Monitoring progress and drafting status reports, and if necessary, preparations for decision making and interventions to secure progress.

Deliverables:

- Steering committee.
- Project and communication plan.
- Status reports and the final report (in collaboration with WP2).

Work Package 2 (WP2): Modelling and Analysis (business analysis and architecture led by SURF)

The objective of WP2 is to identify the inadequacies of the current RDM infrastructure and to provide recommendations for developing RDM infrastructure components and integrations in a feasible and sustainable way, which are beneficial for most SSH research institutes. Modelling of the SSH policy and infrastructure is required to enable effective inventories and (fit-gap) analyses.

For an effective inventory in WP3 we want to:

- Model, understand and determine which policies and infrastructure components are relevant for which RDM phases and specific processes. This is done to assure that

participating institutions don't collect and describe low-level solutions such as storage but focus on RDM functionality researchers need for their research and at the same time can be compliant to policies.

- Determine the method to collect and process the information in a consistent way which makes a broad comparison of the information between the institutes possible. Creating a predefined format covering all aspects of RDM in which the details of the policies and infrastructures and their relationships can be described in the same way will be part of this effort. This will be done in coordination with WP2.

The fit-gap analysis will provide insight in the relationship between the identified RDM policies and the implemented RDM infrastructures. Based on this analysis, we can determine when infrastructure supports policy, and more importantly, when it doesn't. For addressing the RDM infrastructure shortcomings (i.e., gaps), we will take developments in the (inter)national RDM landscape (e.g. ODISSEI/CLARIAH, SURF, EOSC) into account.

The project results will be reported in a document that includes a description of the infrastructure required for policy implementation, the results of the fit-gap analysis, and a set of recommendations for a collaborative approach to establish the missing or underdeveloped infrastructure components. Feedback from the SSH community will be collected and incorporated into the recommendations. The report will be submitted not only to the TDCC-SSH and the LDCCs, but also to the UNL Chiefs of Open Science (COS) and the UNL Bestuurlijk Regieorgaan Open Science (BROS), as these bodies are linked to the university boards and SURF, to promote support and follow-up at both the institutional and national levels.

The main challenges of this work package are feasibility and representativeness. We will take a time-box approach and prioritise the more urgent and common gaps. To increase representativeness, we will use the 'context-rich' use cases (see WP3) as reference and starting point for the fit-gap analysis, which will be extended and validated by the broader inventory of RDM policies and infrastructures, also taking feedback on under-representation into account. For example, how would the use cases have dealt with different (less common) policies or could bottlenecks in the use cases have been solved with alternative (less common) infrastructures used elsewhere?

Activities:

- Determining inventory scope and method (e.g., format, inclusion criteria) for WP3.
- Analyse use cases and institutional (DCC) inventory from WP3 and iteratively refine the model and the structured overview of policy, infrastructure and gaps.
- Analyse national and international developments taking modularity, interoperability, and ease of use into account, to determine opportunities and innovations for resolving the identified gaps.
- Report outcomes to the community for review and refine model and outcomes based on their feedback.

Deliverables:

- Inventory scope and method for WP3.
- Model and structured overview of RDM policy, infrastructure, and gaps.
- Report on analysis and recommendations for RDM innovations addressing common gaps in the SSH domain providing guidance to shape a modular infrastructure advancing RDM for SSH.

Work Package 3 (WP3): SSH Landscape Inventory (coordination and data stewardship led by VU)

The objective of WP3 is to create an overview of the RDM policies and infrastructures that are available to researchers at their SSH institutes. This overview is used for the fit-gap analysis of WP2 but will also be of value for the TDCC-SSH to get insight in where and when policies and supporting infrastructures are common and different. We will use two methods to identify RDM policies,

infrastructures, and bottlenecks: The first method is ‘use-case’ driven allowing to include the rich and various contexts of research projects. Complementary use cases will be selected from both humanities and social sciences. Utrecht University (youth cohort study), VU (social sciences), and UvA (child development and education) already provided use cases, but more will be collected in this WP. The second is a more quantitative method to obtain a broader more detailed and structured overview of applied RDM policies and used RDM infrastructures (with the help of questionnaires/ interviews) enabling comparisons between the SSH institutes.

Activities:

- Collection and selection of complementary SSH use cases and creation of the more quantitative inventory in coordination with WP2.
- Together with the data stewards and (DCC) contacts of the institute/ organisation coordinating the inventories, facilitated by project management (WP1).
- Collection of RDM policy and infrastructure information at the institutes.
- Organise general meetings such as workshops to review (interim) results, facilitated by project management (WP1).
- Compile a comprehensive list of RDM policies and infrastructures in the SSH domain.

Deliverables:

- Use cases & inventory content (e.g., questionnaire/ interview).
- Inventories/ result reviews.
- Structured list of RDM policies and related infrastructures. When available, this list includes:
 - Overview of stakeholders responsible for the institutes policies and/or infrastructures.
 - RDM regulations or guidelines other than policies.
 - Infrastructures not only in use, but also in development or in consideration.
 - RDM bottlenecks institutes are facing, illustrated by the use cases.

The table below gives a high-level overview of the duration of the activities related to the deliverables.

Work Packages	Deliverables	Q1 2025	Q2 2025	Q3 2025	Q4 2025	Q1 2026	Q2 2026
WP1. Project Management							
	WP1.1 Steering Committee						
	WP1.2 Project & Communication Plan						
	WP1.3 Status Reports						
WP2. RDM Modelling & Analysis							
	WP2.1 Inventory Scope & Method						
	WP2.2 RDM Model/Overview for SSH						
	WP2.3 End Report with Recommendations						
WP3. SSH Landscape Inventory							
	WP3.1 Use Cases & Inventory Content						
	WP3.2 Inventories & Reviews						
	WP3.3 RDM Policies & Infrastructures for SSH						

Table 2. Schematic overview of the time to complete the deliverables within the three work packages.

3. Declarations and signature

Funding elsewhere

Have you requested funding for this project elsewhere?

- No
- Yes

Please include details of any additional grants you have requested for this project.

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I have completed this form truthfully;
- I meet the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the ['Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2018'](#)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'F.J. Oort', with a long horizontal stroke extending to the right.

Initial(s) and surname(s): F.J. Oort

Place: Amsterdam

Date: 14-10-2024